
Factors influencing the origin and genesis of terrorism

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Abstract

Terrorism undermines the security of modern societies and poses a growing strategic threat to any country. Terrorist movements are becoming bolder, stronger and more numerous. They are ready to use unlimited violence to cause great human and material damage. The fight against terrorism continues to be a topical issue because it is linked to another very important issue, namely people's lives and health. Terrorism and terrorists are words that are increasingly causing questions to society, the media and individuals. The topicality of the topic is continuous and is caused by the constant attacks, bringing countless victims.

Key words: security, terrorism, terrorist acts, political violence.

Introduction

The most significant challenge for the democratic community is terrorism, which is a multi-layered concept that is related to the socio-economic and political structure of society.

Although many countries are at war with terrorism, clashes with terrorists and terrorist attacks have shaken their social fabric, hampered their economic progress and undermined their political system. Terrorism not only destroys the socio-economic structure of society, but also damages world peace – there is no place in the world that is protected from terrorist attacks.

Results and Discussion

Realizing this, the world and Europe in particular, as the most affected by the migration crisis, parted with the illusion that terrorism is a local phenomenon and a threat only to individual countries. Therefore, in the modern conditions of global society, the effective counteraction to terrorism is not within the power of one state or one structure – regardless of its scale.

Terrorism is not a new phenomenon; it has been used as a tactic and strategy since the beginning of written history and is proving to be relatively difficult to define. Terrorism has been described in various ways, both as a tactic and a strategy, as a crime against humanity, but also as a justified reaction to oppression and resistance, albeit inadequate and bad.

It is obvious that a lot depends on whose point of view it is presented and classified. In this context, it is the common features, such as intimidation, intimidation and violent influence on the opposing side, that characterize terrorism as a phenomenon. That is why the etymology of the very concept, originating from the Latin word “terror” – fear, horror, testifies (Doykov, 2019d).

Terrorism researchers identify the German radical Karl Heinzgen as one of the founders of the theory of modern terrorism.

In 1948 he developed the so-called the “Philosophy of Bombs” theory, which argues that the killing of hundreds or even thousands of people is permissible in the political struggle, as long as it is done in the name of the “highest interests of humanity” (Doykov, 2019d).

Among the most frequently cited publications on terrorism as a phenomenon is *The Causes of Terrorism* (1981) by the famous Martha Crenshaw. In this article, Crenshaw emphasizes the

difficulty of finding common explanations for terrorism and points out that it is possible to distinguish between different types of variables as a starting point for more recent causes.

The purpose of Crenshaw is to outline approaches leading to the analysis of the causes of terrorism, to delineate the “general model of the causal link in the historical aspect” (Concepts of Terrorism), which is based on a comparison between different cases of terrorism.

By demarcating between three groups of variables – strategic, structural and psychological, Crenshaw emphasizes the idea that terrorism is a product of rational political choice.

The conceptual delimitation is the division into structural variables – preconditions and situations.

Assumptions are divided and classified into factors that provide opportunities for terrorism to occur and situations that serve as motivation for direct terrorist acts (Concepts of Terrorism).

Although Crenshaw offers ample ideas for further research and is often cited by others, several scholars have taken on the challenge of developing an understanding of the causes of terrorism at a higher level.

Thus, in the twentieth century, the range of motives for using terrorism as a means of political struggle expanded.

Until then, it was seen as self-sacrifice in the name of some ideals, then for the emerging far-left and far-right terrorist groups, terrorism is becoming a way of self-affirmation.

The manifestations of the “black terror” of the fascists and neo-Nazis do not differ significantly. For both, terrorism is not only a powerful weapon, an instrument, a means of fighting against power, but also a means of gaining and retaining power.

Another influential article published twelve years after Crenshaw's work on Jeffrey Ian Ross. In “The Structural Causes of Opposition Political Terrorism: Towards a Causal Model” (1993), Ross identifies three main categories of causes of terrorism comparable to those of Crenshaw, namely structural and psychological causes, as well as those related to the concept of “rational choice”. Ross concludes that the first generation of causal models, including their own work, may be considered valuable in describing terrorism, but they do not have the means to analyze this phenomenon in depth.

On the nature of terrorism as a collective action, Dipak Gupta (2005) seeks to understand why people engage in such action on behalf of a group on the basis of ethnicity, religion, nationalism or ideology. Gupta presents arguments that are rooted in the economic and socio-psychological dimensions of human motivation.

In order to distinguish between constructs that represent dissatisfaction and those that lead to violence, Gupta points out that “Political violence takes place when the leader gives his voice to dissatisfaction – dissatisfaction – through forms of dissatisfaction. us “and” them “for building a collective identity”” (Gupta, Mndra, 2005, 573-598).

In other words, political, economic and religious grievances are not in themselves factors that lead to terrorism.

The reasons in this way may remain hidden until a mechanism is triggered that leads to violence.

For the characterization of certain actions such as terror, the historical time of the event and the point of view for evaluation are important.

Contradictory assessments are often given of the same historical actions, defining them as terror or as a form of political struggle and social resistance. On this occasion, Prof. Vasil Prodanov writes: “The difference is in the assessments given to them, according to different interests, ideologies, values” (Doykov, 2019c).

Terrorism is basically a strategy and a tactic – a kind of political war aimed at political results.

It qualifies as a low-intensity conflict and can be described as a military action at the lower end of the range of violence. This is the level where political, economic and psychological motives play a more significant role than conventional military force (Trifonov, 2003).

There is almost a consensus on the common factors that give rise to terrorism.

They can be represented as: political; economically; historical; social (poverty, disregard for human rights through repression and acts of intolerance and violence on ethnic grounds); Presence of

a crisis (revolutionary) situation (left-wing, right-wing, separatist – often influenced by a certain ideology); foreign patronage.

The specific factors influencing the origin and genesis of terrorism are determined by the specific political and social environment in the individual geopolitical regions. Such are, for example, the factors influencing terrorism as a phenomenon in the Middle East and North Africa: the Arab-Israeli conflict; the Palestinian problem; religious extremism; the contradictions in Arab politics; the East-West confrontation; anti-Western sentiments.

On the occasion of the Arab-Israeli conflict, former US ambassador to the United Nations Alan Keyes said that he was part of the global war on terror.

At a conference in Jerusalem, he expressed the following position: “Peace is not possible and there should be no pursuit of peace with terrorists. We do not want them to cease to exist. That is why there is no alternative to victory in this war” (Doykov, 2019c).

According to Keyes, the culture of terrorism has developed so far thanks to the fact that Western countries have not reacted in the necessary way when terrorism was directed against Jews and Israel. “But if we cannot name the Palestinian terrorist, then we lose the moral clarity without which the war on terror loses its all-encompassing character. In this way, our victory in this war becomes very dubious” (Doykov, 2019c).

According to him, the issue of Israel’s war against terrorists must be raised – when there is a war and one side seeks to destroy the other, and the second says that its goal is peace, its goal. “Peace cannot be the main goal of war. Such a goal can only be victory over the enemy. Moreover, it is a war on terrorists. Of course, we want peace, because we know how good it is to live in peace, what can be done and created.

But it is impossible to demand peace with terrorists, because this will not be life and there will be no peace.

We cannot and must not reconcile with terrorists.

We want them to cease to exist. That is why there is no alternative to victory in this war” (Israel can negotiate with terrorists).

To strike terrorism in his heart does not mean to destroy the Palestinians, but to cure the causes of the phenomenon. Because extremism does not exist in itself as such, it is a reaction to oppression.

If freedom of religion exists in one country, religious extremism will lose its fertile ground.

Considering the contradictions in Arab politics, it should be noted that a number of international organizations have united around the formation of a global coalition to fight terrorism. Among them are the United Nations, NATO, the European Union (EU), the Organization of American States (OAS), the Association of South Asian Nations, the Arab League, and the Organization of the Islamic Conference.

The active position and actions of the North Atlantic Treaty Organization are important for the successes achieved in the fight against international terrorism over the last decade.

The NATO operation in Afghanistan is particularly significant in this regard. The war against the Taliban regime also demonstrated the need for organizations of this type.

However, the war against Iraq has revealed some difficulties in building a common front against terrorism, not so much to maintain common positions and goals of the international community as to the means to achieve them. Despite controversy among some members of the alliance, NATO retains its capabilities as a leading defense alliance that will play a key role in the fight against terrorism in the coming years.

At the moment, civil society groups are considered to be an effective option in resolving conflicts.

Terrorism is an obvious state of climax in the human conflict that arises when violence enters the matter.

Terrorism is the result of problems that have arisen in resolving conflicts. This is crucial for the social problems of society. Each of the stakeholders must play its part in the fight against terrorism. Thus, the role of civil society in the fight against terrorism is inevitable.

Almost all of them are directly and indirectly part of civil society groups, especially specialists from all disciplines.

Because the fight against terrorism requires both the pre-conflict stage and the post-conflict one.

It is also important to increase anti-terrorist movements before the damage occurs. In the same way, if the conflict leads to terrorism and violence after that, the victims deserve practical support.

Civil society can oppose terrorism as a social evil. It should advocate for its governments to reduce socio-economic injustice, poverty and inequality, which are the main causes of terrorism.

Factors influencing the development of terrorism in Europe are (Doykov, 2019c):

- separatist sentiments within individual countries;
- presence of compact groups of immigrants from high-risk countries;
- opportunity for wide and fast public response to terrorist acts.

The influence of separatist sentiments on the territory of Europe is mostly found in Albania, Kosovo and Macedonia. There are such in the Caucasus in regions such as Abkhazia, South Ossetia, Adjara – in this zone, neutral for Russian interests.

As for the presence of compact groups of immigrants, it can be said that there have been such groups in Europe for a long time.

At the moment, Turks and Serbs are the most numerous compact groups of emigrants in Germany.

After the fall of the Berlin Wall, fears arose that 10 million people would head to the West, but this did not happen in the end. However, minorities do not cause crises in democracies, while in non-democracies they create problems.

In non-democracies, some minorities live in fear because they have been subjected to repression and discrimination for decades and are afraid to do anything.

The difference is that when minorities take action in an undemocratic authoritarian state, those actions are likely to be violent – in the form of riots. This is one of the results of the transition to democracy.

Minorities who have been forced to be passive in the past are suddenly given the opportunity to have their voices heard, and they are more politically active, more inclined to protest.

This is why it is sometimes argued that the transition to democracy can be dangerous. However, it should not be forgotten that the “minorities” who are politically active are usually disadvantaged.

These are people who once came as immigrants, or were conquered, people who have historical reasons to revolt.

And then the question arises whether the states are ready to join them or to suppress them (Risk minorities).

Conclusions

Terrorism is not a new phenomenon in human experience. Violence has been used throughout human history by those who have chosen to oppose states, kings and princes.

This type of violence is different from what is defined as terrorism. Violence in opposition to the government is often directed against soldiers and those in power.

Terrorism, however, is characterized by the use of violence against civilians, with a strong desire to cause fear or panic among the population. Terrorism is not unique to the twentieth and twenty-first centuries.

It also existed in the eighteenth century in revolutionary France, as well as among the zealots of Palestine in opposition to Roman rule around 2000 BC.

Today, terrorist activity can be detected anywhere in the world.

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